

CEDA Metadata

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CEDA Metadata Catalogue

Generating Metadata

Publishing Metadata

Metadata Consumers

Community

CEDA Metadata Catalogue

All of CEDA data holdings are catalogued in a database according to a data model (MOLES2/3).

This model quantifies various aspects of the data:

- What is it? (i.e. instrument, format, model, service)
- Where and when is it? (i.e. spatial coverage, date range/times)
- Who owns it/where did it come from? (i.e. Who created the dataset? Restrictions on usage – UK only?)
- What can it do? (i.e. Is it available in a visualisation service? Any legal aspects?)
- Any associated resources? (i.e. Keyword or Parameter names, Links to original data provider site, documentation, Web Service Endpoints)

CEDA Metadata Catalogue

Information in the data catalogue is created by a combination of manual entry by Data Scientists as well as information taken from the data itself during the ingestion process and placement on the CEDA archive.

Metadata in the catalogue is used for a variety of purposes:

- Provide a resource to generate metadata for external consumption i.e. to aid data “discovery”, allow data/CEDA services to be used in external resources (i.e. WFS, WMS etc)
- Provide an accurate up to date description of each dataset and any related issues as a resource for the community
- Reference – allow citation of dataset (DOI)
- Dataset management

CEDA Metadata Catalogue

Search - Windows Internet Explorer

http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/search/

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Search for Met Office MIDAS stations NERC Data Discovery service A-Z page index

- Search data

To search for datasets held at the BADC and NEODC use the search box below. You can use the wildcard character * to indicate zero or more characters and ? to indicate exactly one character. For example, 'rain*' will match both 'rain' and 'rainfall'. 'air?' will match 'airs' but not 'air'.

airf in All Search

- Search BADC website

To search the BADC website use the search box below. You can use the * character to match zero or more characters. You can also enter multiple terms separated by 'and' or 'or'. For example, 'rain and snow' will find 'rain' and 'snow'.

Search

- Dataset Index

Full list of datasets held at the BADC. You can apply for access to datasets from this page.

- Search the NERC Data Catalogue Service

The NERC Data Catalogue Service allows you to search for related data across all NERC data centres.

- Search for Met Office MIDAS stations

Search for Met Office surface stations using a variety of methods, including an interactive map.

- A-Z index of BADC webpages.

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z

Home Contact Disclaimer Last Modified: 04/17/2012 13:59:43

Users can search
CEDA Catalogue
from homepage

search term, 'arsf' [6 results found]

er ID	Created	Type	Title
nc.ac.uk	2007-02-16	Data Entity	Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF) data
nc.ac.uk	2011-08-17	Data Entity	European Facility for Airborne Research in Environmental and Geo-sciences (EUFAR)
nc.ac.uk	2010-04-19	Data Entity	Eyjafjallajokull - Volcanic Ash Cloud Measurements
nc.ac.uk	2005-11-14	Data Entity	Aerosol and Chemical Transport in Tropical Convection (ACTIVE)
nc.ac.uk	2006-11-03	Data Entity	Met Office Met. Research Flight C-130 data
nc.ac.uk	2008-09-09	Data Entity	FAAM - VOCALS-UK - VAMOS (Variability of the American Monsoon System) Ocean Cloud Atmosphere Land Study Regional Experiment

Will search across all catalogue holdings depending on search semantics.

CEDA Catalogue is based on MOLES data model that links the concept of a data entity (aka "dataset") with related objects such as the "observation station" (i.e. plane), data tool (i.e. radar), activity (i.e. whole campaign) and the "deployment" (i.e. flight).

Users can navigate this structure to find the data they want/ related information i.e. On this mission/deployment what other instrument available?

CEDA Metadata Catalogue

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the following content:

Viewing Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF) data - Windows Internet Explorer
 http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/neodc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dataent_11716368890815055

The page content includes:

- Links to further information and references** (circled in red):
 - [NEODC ARSF website](#) contains details about instruments and current flight campaigns.
 - [NEODC ARSF tutorial](#), an overview of the ARSF and data processing techniques, explaining how to use the georectification software AZGCROR.
 - [NEODC website](#) which contains notes on how to use [AZGCROR](#) for georectification after atmospheric correction.
 - [Camera calibration certificates](#) for the ARSF camera are available in PDF format.
 - [Link for Landscape Modelling \(LUM\)](#), University of Cambridge website.
 - [LIDAR manufacturer website](#).
- Citation**:

Natural Environment Research Council Airborne Research and Survey Facility - Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF) Aerial Photography, Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM), Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) and Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI 2) data, [Internet]. NERC Earth Observation Data Centre, 2007. Date of citation. Available from http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/neodc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dataent_11716368890815055
- Who to contact**:

If you have queries about these pages or about obtaining the ARSF data from the NEODC then you should contact [NEODC Support](#). Your query should be answered within one working day. When follow-up work is required, the NEODC support will carry out the work as quickly and efficiently as possible, and in any case, the user will be kept informed of progress.
- Lineage**:

Data have been provided to NEODC via a number of routes: Most data up to 2005 was provided directly from ARSF flight team (ARSF-Ops) or Andrew Wilson at CEH, on various media. Data since 2008 was mostly transferred to NEODC from ARSF-Data Analysis Node (DAN) in Plymouth via rsync. Data for 2006 - 2008 were provided partly from ARSF-DAN, partly from ARSF-Ops, and some from Andrew Wilson. Data from the ULM LIDAR instrument was provided, via FTP or on media, from ULM Cambridge. Scanned aerial photographs were provided by Bluesky Ltd, who carried out the digitisation, on LaCIE disks. Some data ("user-provided") was sent to NEODC by ARSF data users.
- Quality Statement**:

unknown
- Author**:

Name: Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF)
 email: arsf@nerc.ac.uk
 URL: <http://arsf.nerc.ac.uk/>
- Online References**:

Relation	Title
Visualisation	NEODC Interactive Map
Documentation	NEODC ARSF Tutorial
Documentation	NEODC ARSF website
Documentation	AZGCROR Software
Documentation	ARSF Data Directory
Apply for access	Apply for access to ARSF datasets
Logo	NEODC Logo
- Parent Data Entity**:

No data specified at present
- Sub Data Entities**:

None
- Associated Deployments**:

Loading deployments info...
- Data coverage**:

Spatial coverage: No spatial coverage information available.
 Temporal coverage: No temporal information available.

Links to further information.

- External sites
- Access restrictions
- How to apply for access
- Contact point for help

Links to other MOLES data objects

Get Data

Username: *Not logged in*
Current directory: / [neodc](#) / [arsf](#)

Download multiple files [How to use](#) Depth: 1

Dataset: [Airborne Research and Survey Facility \(ARSF\) data](#) [Details](#)

NERC ARSF - Airborne Research and Survey Facility

- [00README](#) 101 bytes
- [1981](#)
- [1982](#)
- [1983](#)
- [1984](#)
- [1985](#)
- [1986](#)
- [1987](#)
- [1988](#)
- [1989](#)
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- [2001](#)

Download data!

Science & Technology

Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF) data - Windows Internet Explorer

http://tranquil.badc.rl.ac.uk:50001/editAtom/neodc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dataent_117163688

File Favorites Tools Help

Go Bookmarks Settings

Sea... Mer... Mer... Sug... Res... ORA... DDS FOO... Ste... Web... Dat... NERC DMAG

Home

British Atmospheric Centre

CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Help

Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF) data

[DC Browse](#) [Edit CEDA specific information](#)

Data Entity
neodc.nerc.ac.uk
2009-12-10 03:01
2011-12-23 17:08
[/db/atoms/published/data_entities/neodc.nerc.ac.uk/dataent_11716368890815055.atom](#)

Info

Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF) data

Measurement

ARSF

Published

Update

[Add/Edit](#)

[Add/Edit](#)

Internet 85%

CEDA users: edit information.

CEDA Metadata Catalogue

New updated catalogue: MOLES3 – improved catalogue data model, significantly improved editor and user/search/results pages

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the CEDA Metadata Catalogue. The browser's address bar shows the URL www.ceda.ac.uk/datacat/cov/893. The page header includes the Science & Technology Facilities Council logo and the text "Centre for Environmental Data Archival". Below the header is a search bar with the text "Search for:" and a search button. The main content area displays a record for "Data from GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site". The record includes a "Record Status" section indicating the dataset is citable and available from 2007-09-20. There are sections for "Download & Services" (with a "Data directory for GBS data from Sparsholt:" link), "Citation" (providing a full citation for the dataset), "Previous Identifiers Used" (listing a DOI), "Keywords" (listing "Meteorological geographical features"), and "Description" (providing a detailed overview of the GBS dataset). An "Additional Information" section at the bottom lists a link to the "CEDA MOLES2 Metadata Catalogue Entry". The browser's status bar at the bottom shows a download of a file named "140749349426" which has been canceled.

CEDA Metadata "pipeline"

External Users NERC Catalogue Service, DataCite, UK Location Portal, Go-Geo, MEDIN Portal, INSPIRE.... All use metadata from CEDA metadata publishing layer

CEDA is required to publish metadata describing its data holdings:

- The NERC Catalogue Service requires XML compliant to UK Gemini 2.2
- INSPIRE compliancy via UK Location Portal
- DataCite: CEDA has DOI's for certain datasets, details must be published according to DataCite

Many consumers.. CEDA as a NERC data centre, holding public data, has legal requirements to make conformant metadata available.

Many CEDA datasets can be visualised as a WMS endpoint i.e via the Visualisation Service.

CEDA publishes its data via OAI-PMH2, OGC CSW, Web Accessible Folder (in progress).

Publishing Metadata

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the Data Catalogue Service search interface. The browser's address bar shows the URL `data-search.nerc.ac.uk/search/full`. The page features a header with the text "Data Catalogue Service sharing NERC data" and a navigation menu. On the left, there are links for "About the DCS", "Search for data", and "Results". The main content area is titled "Search for data" and includes instructions: "Please use one or more of the options below to search the catalogue. Alternatively, try our advanced text search." There are three search methods: 1) "Free text" search with a text input field and "Search" and "Clear" buttons; 2) "Date range" search with "From" and "To" input fields and "Search" and "Clear" buttons; 3) "Geographic search" with a "Countries" dropdown menu and "Search" and "Clear area" buttons. Below the geographic search is a map of the world. At the bottom of the browser window, a download bar shows a "download" button and a "Canceled" message.

About the DCS
 Search for data
 Results

Results

RSS Atom

Your search returned **4** results. Showing **all results** (help).

You are searching for...

documents containing arsf
4 results returned in 0.20 seconds.

Edit this search

Bookmark these results with:

20 the number of results per page.

view geographic coverage

Dataset description	Resource type	Online resource
<p>1. European Facility for Airborne Research in Environmental and Geo-sciences (EUFAR) Data from the projects and training under the EUFAR project. EUFAR (European Facility for Airborne Research in Environmental and Geo-sciences) is an Integrating Activity of the 7th Framework Program of the European Commission. EUFAR... [more]</p>	series	yes
<p>2. FREE - Local flood forecasting capability for fluvial and estuarine floods: Use of GridStix for constraining uncertainty in predictive models The Local flood forecasting capability for fluvial and estuarine floods: Use of GridStix for constraining uncertainty in predictive models Project is a NERC Flood Risk for Extreme Events (FREE) Research Programme project (Round 1 - NE/E002439/1 - ... [more]</p>	series	yes
<p>3. Airborne Research and Survey Facility (ARSF) data The Airborne Research & Survey Facility (ARSF, formerly Airborne Remote Sensing Facility) is managed by NERC Scientific Services and Programme Management. It provides the UK environmental science community, and other potential users, with the mean... [more]</p>	series	yes
<p>4. Eyjafjallajokull - Volcanic Ash Cloud Measurements The Icelandic Volcano, Eyjafjallajokull, starting erupting on 14th April 2010. The volcanic ash cloud produced covered much of Northern Europe for several weeks causing extensive disruption to air travel. The UK and</p>	series	yes

download

Publishing Metadata

The image shows a sequence of three browser screenshots illustrating the process of publishing metadata in the Data Catalogue Service (DCS).

Top Screenshot: Shows the search results page for the query "arsf&sd=&ed=&t=co&a=OpenLayers.Control.LayerSwitcher_45_baseLayers=Bath". The search results list several documents, including "1. European Facility for Airborne Research (EFAR) Data from the 1st under the ELPA Airborne Research as an Integrative of the European".

Middle Screenshot: Shows the search results page with the search criteria changed to "arsf&sd=&ed=&t=co&a=OpenLayers.Control.LayerSwitcher_45_baseLayers=Bath". The search results list several documents, including "1. European Facility for Airborne Research (EFAR) Data from the 1st under the ELPA Airborne Research as an Integrative of the European".

Bottom Screenshot: Shows the details page for the document "meodc.nerc.ac.uk_NERC_DMS_0.7_0ai115Aceda.nerc.ac.uk%3Adataent_117163688". The page includes a title, abstract, and a list of metadata fields. A red box highlights the "Temporal coverage" field, which contains the text "These data span the period from 1979 to 2000". A red arrow points from a text box to this field.

Text Box: A red box contains the text "Link from NERC DCS back to Data Centre".

Discovery Records in UK Gemini 2.2 format to be published via OGC CSW to the UK Location Portal for EU INSPIRE compliancy

The screenshot shows the UK Location Portal website. The browser address bar is 'location.defra.gov.uk'. The page has a navigation menu with 'Home page', 'Resource Centre', 'News', 'Programme', 'Council', and 'INSPIRE'. A sidebar on the left lists 'Defra home', 'UK Location', 'Resource Centre', 'News', 'Programme', 'Council', and 'INSPIRE'. The main content area features a large aerial photograph of a road interchange. Below the image, there is a 'Welcome to UK Location' section and a 'Governance' section. A sidebar on the right contains 'Latest updates' and 'Latest resources' sections. At the bottom of the page, there is a 'Tag Cloud' with terms like 'AGI', 'SS', 'SIG', 'Data Provider', 'Data Publisher', 'Data Users', 'Discovery Metadata Service', 'GEMINI v2.1', 'Getting Started', and 'INSPIRE LGA'.

CEDA Metadata Associations

CEDA works in unison with other NERC data centres on ensuring that metadata content conforms with required standards

NERC metadata services on behalf of NERC, others (MEDIN)

Operate OAI/CSW Harvesters

- Ingest metadata into a searchable catalogue
- Underpins the NERC Data Catalogue Service portal (similar for MEDIN – Marine Environment Data Information Network)

Through NERC partners and contacts, CEDA collaborates on various metadata content working groups

- UK Gemini
- INSPIRE (CEDA is an INSPIRE LMO)